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3-BENZAZEPINONE DERIVATIVES: ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND ITS STRUCTURE ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP (SAR) STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

A series of 3-benzazepinone (3-BZ) derivatives were tested for their *in vitro* antioxidant efficacy by DPPH and LPO assays and compared with standard Butylated Hydroxyl Anisole (BHA). The derivatives containing electron donating groups *viz.*, OH, OCH₃ were found to be good antioxidants compared to BHA. While, the compounds containing electron withdrawing moiety *viz.*, NO₂, Cl, Br, and F were found to be less active compared to standard BHA. The structure activity relationship studies suggest that the electron donating moieties majorly contribute to the anti-oxidant property of the potent compounds. Furthermore, analogs and more variants of the potent molecules can be synthesized to test for better antioxidants with lesser IC₅₀ values.

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INTRODUCTION

Extensive research in heterocyclic compounds can be attributed to the vastness and wide array of applications in pharmacy, medicine, agriculture, and other fields. The chemistry of heterocyclic compounds is as relevant as that of aliphatic or aromatic compounds. Their study is of great interest both from the theoretical as well as practical study point. Nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur are the most common heteroatoms. Among all nitrogen containing heterocycles, seven membered nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds, in particular, 3-benzazepinones exhibit broad biological significance for example as γ -secretase inhibitors [1], bradycardia agents [2] and it also serves as remedies to several diseases like Parkinson's, cancer, muscular pain and cardiovascular diseases [3-8] etc.,

Antioxidants are of great importance because of their potentials as therapeutic agents in many diseases. Excessive oxidative stress is mainly responsible for the generation of free radicals. Free radicals play a major role in heart disease, cancer, strokes, Parkinson's diseases and allergies [9, 10]. However, increased levels of free radicals can cause damage to proteins, DNA, lipids and cell membranes [11]. Thus minimizing the formation of free radicals may be fundamental approach to the primary prevention of these diseases. Since antioxidants may inhibit the formation of free radicals, designing synthetic compounds having capabilities to reduce the formation of free radicals is of considerable interest as potent antioxidant agents.

Prompted by all these observations and keeping the therapeutic importance of antioxidants research in human health and in continuation of our research interest in the development of compounds with a wide range of physicochemical and biological properties [12-18]. Here in, we report the 3-BZ derivatives as promising antioxidants.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Ascorbic acid, 2-thiobarbituric acid (TBA), 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Co., USA. All the other chemicals and reagents were purchased from Merck chemicals. Synthesis of 3-BZ [3(a-k)] derivatives (Table 1) was achieved by the previously reported procedure [19].

BIOLOGICAL STUDIES

In vitro antioxidant activity

DPPH free radical scavenging assay

Different concentrations of standard BHA and 3-BZ derivatives were prepared in distilled ethanol. One ml of each compound solution having different concentrations (10 μ M, 25 μ M, 50 μ M, 100 μ M, and 500 μ M) were taken in individual test tubes; 4 ml of 0.1 mM ethanol solution of DPPH was added and shaken vigorously. The tubes were then incubated in the dark room at room temperature for 20 min. A DPPH blank was prepared without compound and ethanol was used for baseline correction. Changes (decrease) in the absorbance at 517 nm were measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer, and the remaining DPPH was calculated. The percent decrease in the absorbance was recorded for each concentration and percent quenching of DPPH was calculated on the basis of its absorbance. The radical scavenging activity was expressed as the inhibition percentage and was calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Radical scavenging activity (\%)} = [(A_0 - A_1)/A_0 \times 100]$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance blank, without compound and A_1 is the absorbance of the solution containing compounds.

Microsomal lipid peroxidation (LPO) assay

Liver excised from adult male wister rats, were homogenized with a polytron (speed setting 7-8) in 10 ml of ice cold Tris-HCl buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4) by the method of [20]. The homogenate was centrifuged at 14000 rpm for 15 min. The supernatants (1 ml) were incubated with different concentration of compounds (10 μ M, 25 μ M, 50 μ M, 100 μ M, 200 μ M and 500 μ M) in the presence of 10 μ M FeSO₄ and 1.0 Mm ascorbic acid at 37 °C for 1 hr. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 1.0 ml of trichloroacetic acid (TCA; 28 %) and 1.5 ml of thiobarbituric acid (TBA; 1 %). The solution was heated at 100 °C for 15 min, cooled to room temperature, and centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 15 min, and the color of the malondialdehyde (MDA)-TBA complex in the supernatant was read at 532 nm using a spectrophotometer. BHA has used a positive control. The inhibition ratio (%) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Inhibition ratio (\%)} = (A - A_1)/A \times 100,$$

Where A is the absorbance of the control and A_1 is the absorbance of the test sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The *in vitro* antioxidant efficacy of synthesized 3-BZ derivatives were evaluated based on the DPPH [20] and LPO [21] assays. These results were recorded for each test compound as IC₅₀ values accessible in the Table 2. The BHA was used as standard for antioxidant activity. Results revealed that among all the tested compounds, compound **3c** with an IC₅₀ of 14.3 \pm 0.58 which is better compared to BHA which showed an IC₅₀ of 15.8 \pm 0.52 in DPPH assay. Also, with the LPO assay it was noticed that **3c** has better IC₅₀ of 16.1 \pm 0.36 compared to BHA with IC₅₀ of 17.6 \pm 0.34. The potent antioxidant activity of **3c** can be attributed to the electron donating OH group. On the other hand, compounds **3a**, **3b** and **3k** in the order of **3k**>**3a**>**3b** showed moderate antioxidant potentials. Furthermore, the compounds *viz.*, **3j**, **3d**, **3g**, **3h**, **3f**, and **3e** containing electron withdrawing groups like NO₂, Br, Cl and F showed low antioxidant activities whereas compound **3i** having no substitution on phenyl ring showed moderate activity compared to other synthesized derivatives as well as standard BHA.

Table 1: Structure of the 3-benzazepinone derivatives 3(a-k)

Compound No	Structure
3a	
3b	
3c	
3d	
3e	
3f	
3g	
3h	
3i	
3j	
3k	

Table 2: Antioxidant activities of 3-benzazepinone derivatives 3(a-k)

Compound	DPPH activity: IC ₅₀ (μM/ ml)	LPO inhibition: IC ₅₀ (μM/ ml)
3a	32.1 ± 0.62	36 ± 0.71
3b	41.2 ± 0.53	44.2 ± 0.41
3c	14.3 ± 0.58	16.1 ± 0.36
3d	72.1 ± 0.28	76 ± 0.51
3e	118.2 ± 0.78	120.5 ± 0.82
3f	101.3 ± 0.18	105.4 ± 0.49
3g	83.2 ± 0.61	87.3 ± 0.74
3h	94.3 ± 0.62	99.5 ± 0.35
3i	48.9 ± 0.45	50.2 ± 0.53
3j	65.2 ± 0.32	71.1 ± 0.68
3k	24.3 ± 0.44	26.4 ± 0.37
BHA	15.8 ± 0.52	17.6 ± 0.34

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, among a series of **3-benzazepinone derivatives 3(a-k)** synthesized with different substituent as per our previous studies [19], compounds containing electron donating groups like OH, OCH₃ were found to be good antioxidants compared to the standard BHA. While, the compounds containing electron withdrawing moiety such as NO₂, Cl, Br, and F were found to possess less activity compared to standard BHA. The results indicated from structure activity relationship studies suggest that the electron donating moieties majorly contribute to the antioxidant property of the potent compounds. Synthesis of more variants/analogs of such compounds can be undertaken to establish a series of potent antioxidant molecules.

ABBREVIATIONS

3-BZ	: 3-benzazepinone
DPPH	: 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl
LPO	: Lipid per oxidation
TLC	: Thin layer chromatography
CDCl ₃	: Deuterated Chloroform
TMS	: Tetramethylsilane
HBTU	: (N, N, N', N'-Tetramethyl-O-(1H-benzotriazol-1-yl)uranium hexafluorophosphate
DMF	: Dimethylformamide
BHA	: Butylated hydroxyl anisole
TBA	: Thiobarbituric acid
TCA	: Trichloroacetic acid

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Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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